

Studies on the Co-ordination Chemistry of Rhenium Part III.—Hexakis (methylisocyano) Rhenium(II) nitrate

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Methylation¹ of $\text{Ag}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]$ with CH_3I gives an insoluble gray coloured residue which is not identical in appearance with AgI . This compound, insoluble in all common solvents is isolated by repeated washing with methanol and ether to free it from the other soluble products. This compound on heating with moderately dilute HNO_3 gives fumes of iodine with a yellow coloured residue of AgI indicating the presence of iodine salt. Thus it may be presumed that during the alkylation of $\text{Ag}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]$, along with the formation of some soluble isonitrile complexes, an addition compound between silver iodide and the iodide of hexakis(methylisocyano)rhenium(II) is formed. The alkylation reaction may be written as below.

The weight of the addition product is found to be 8.1 g starting from 5 g of $\text{Ag}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]$ which corresponds very closely with the formation of the above mentioned reaction. The soluble non-electrolyte and electrolyte isomers of the empirical formula $[(\text{CH}_3\text{NC})_4\text{Re}(\text{CN})_2]$ have been fully characterised with the help of chemical, magnetic, spectral including n.m.r. studies. The electrolytic form has been further confirmed by separating the cationic and anionic parts of the complex and thus forming simple salts with the help of ion exchangers. However, these will be discussed as part II of this series, elsewhere. All the above mentioned soluble compounds are mixed ligand complexes. In this communication the formation of a hexakisicyanide complex is presented starting from the insoluble adduct.

The double salt, isolated from the methylation¹ of $\text{Ag}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]$ is analysed. A typical analysis is given. Found : total AgI , 92.0% ; free AgI , 73.9% ; $[(\text{CH}_3\text{NC})_6\text{Re}] \text{I}_2$, 8 AgI requires: total AgI 91.58% ; free AgI , 73.23%.

The double salt begins to decompose in presence of alkalis with the evolution of methylisocyanide but with dilute nitric acid and silver nitrate it gives the following reaction

Stoichiometric amounts of the double salt and powdered AgNO_3 are digested in very dilute ($0.005 M$) HNO_3 medium on a water bath at 90° for about 2 hrs cautiously. When all the AgNO_3 is consumed, the mixture is cooled and filtered. The filtrate is allowed to concentrate in vacuum over caustic alkali. The concentrated solution is treated with acetone and vigorously stirred when an orange oil is formed, which is separated from the mother liquor by decantation. The oily layer is dissolved in minimum quantity of water and reprecipitated with acetone. This process is repeatedly done till the washed liquor is free from acid. The oil is further treated with absolute alcohol, when it solidified to a yellow powder and this is kept over P_2O_5 in vacuum to a constant weight and analysed. Found : Re, 33.55% : NO_3 , 22.0% : total N, 20.24% : $[(\text{CH}_3\text{NC})_6\text{Re}](\text{NO}_3)_2$. Requires : Re, 33.49% : NO_3 , 22.3% ; total N, 20.13%.

The compound is highly hygroscopic in nature. Aqueous solution of this compound slowly decomposes with the evolution of methyl isocyanide. Alkali brings the decomposition quicker with a dark violet intermediate colouration which slowly fades to a colourless solution. This isonitrile complex is exceptionally stable in acidic medium. This is due to the presence of acid which prevents hydrolysis. Unlike to other cyano complexes of divalent rhenium, $[(\text{CH}_3\text{NC})_6\text{Re}]^{2+}$ ion is exceptionally stable towards oxidation and even acid $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ or MnO_4^- cannot oxidise it into heptavalent perrhenate stage. Aqueous solution of hexakis(methylisocyano) rhenium(II) nitrate gives insoluble yellow precipitates with many anions i.e. PtCl_6^{2-} , ClO_4^- and $[\text{HgI}_4]^{2-}$. The absorption spectrum in dilute HNO_3 medium shows a broad band in the region of $420 m\mu$ and two sharp maxima at $243 m\mu$ and $221 m\mu$ in the U.V. region. Like other cyano and mixed cyano complexes of divalent rhenium, the non-hygroscopic chloroplatinate of hexakis(methylisocyano) rhenium(II) is feebly paramagnetic (0.45 B.M.) at 301°K . The infra-red spectrum of this chloroplatinate salt shows isocyanide stretching at 2185 cm^{-1} . Further works are in progress. The author expresses his grateful thanks to Prof. P. B. Sarkar and Dr. P. Bandyopadhyay of the University of Calcutta for their kind suggestions and providing laboratory facilities.

REFERENCE

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